

Realistic Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Simulation: A Comprehensive Approach

David Tejero-Ruiz¹, Francisco J. Pérez-Grau¹, Antidio Viguria¹ and Aníbal Ollero²

Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive software architecture that facilitates the testing and deployment of autonomous missions in the context of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) simulation. Our approach integrates and enhances several tools, including the Robot Operating System (ROS), to create a robust environment for evaluating autonomous UAV operations and gathering data. The core of our simulation framework leverages Unreal Engine and the AirSim plugin to model UAV dynamics and generate sensor data. Various modifications have been implemented to enhance sensor fidelity and enable realistic movement of diverse world objects, achieving a higher degree of realism. Designed for high configurability, the proposed architecture allows for flexible adaptation to a wide range of scenarios and requirements. Thus, this simulation environment supports rigorous testing and development of autonomous UAV systems, presenting a valuable platform for researchers and developers in the field of aerial robotics.

Index Terms—Unreal Engine, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, Software-in-the-Loop (SITL), AirSim, Aerial Robotics, Robot Operating System (ROS).

I. INTRODUCTION

IN robotics, accurate simulation of autonomous systems is crucial for improving their performance in real-world scenarios. Simulation tools play an important role by allowing researchers and developers to gather data for algorithm training and validate complete autonomous missions. For example, these tools facilitate the evaluation of navigation strategies, the planning of complex missions, or the design of obstacle avoidance algorithms.

Moreover, the simulation of sensor data is commonly used to train perception models. Improvements in simulation quality directly enhance the performance of these perception-based algorithms, contributing to a better understanding of the environment when deploying these systems in real-world scenarios. Developing more accurate localization and detection techniques through simulation will help to build more reliable and cost-effective robotics solutions.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), especially multi-rotors, are becoming increasingly useful for a variety of tasks due to their ability to reduce human risk and efficiently handle repetitive activities. These applications range from surveillance or warehouse inventory management to operating in dangerous environments, such as infrastructure inspection or search and rescue missions. Accurately simulating their behaviour in

Fig. 1: Simulation of an autonomous mission in a refinery environment. 3D view (top left), LiDAR-based SLAM (bottom left), RGB image (top right) and depth image (bottom right).

complex scenarios can help in optimizing their performance and ensuring safety. An example of an autonomous mission running in our simulation framework is depicted in Fig. 1.

II. RELATED WORK

Various simulation tools are utilized for robotics research [1], including Gazebo [2], which is integrated into the Robot Operating System (ROS) [3], and Carla [4], which emphasizes autonomous driving. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of simulation in aerial robotics research is hindered by the difficulty in accurately replicating real-world dynamics [5].

One approach to address these challenges is AirSim [6], an open-source project developed by Microsoft. AirSim operates within Unreal Engine [7] or Unity [8], providing solutions to the main challenges of UAV simulation. The core of our approach is built on AirSim and Unreal Engine due to AirSim's extensive capabilities, access to its internal code, and Unreal Engine's photorealism, as we will discuss further.

Noteworthy works on UAV simulation tools include Hector [9] and RotorS [10], both built on Gazebo. While these tools support the simulation of various multi-rotor models and offer adequate sensor simulation and full integration with the ROS ecosystem, Gazebo's limited rendering capabilities constrain photorealistic simulation and efficient dynamics simulation.

Other works leverage NVIDIA Isaac Gym [11] to build parallelized robotic simulations for training reinforcement learning algorithms. Although it is extensively used for articulated robots, the fidelity of aerial robot models is insufficient for complex tasks. Works such as [12] address this challenge

¹CATEC (Advanced Center for Aerospace Technologies), Calle Wilbur y Orville Wright, 19, La Rinconada, 41309 Sevilla, Spain; [dtejero, fjperz, aviguria]@catec.aero

²Robotics, Vision and Control Group (GRVC), Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain; aollero@us.es

Fig. 2: Simulation architecture including the main software modules.

by developing new models of sensors and rotors, integrating them with simulated flight controller instances.

FlightMare [13] achieves high-frequency simulation of quadrotors by separating the rendering and physics engines. This particular work uses Unity and a custom flexible physics engine for dynamics simulation. However, it lacks support for many of the sensors and control modes offered by AirSim.

Therefore, after reviewing the state-of-the-art in simulation tools, we chose AirSim and Unreal Engine as the core of our scheme. Unreal Engine offers robust support for building photorealistic scenarios, providing easy access to a wide range of assets and built environments. AirSim integrates seamlessly with Unreal Engine projects, providing valuable tools for realistic UAV simulation, such as Software-In-The-Loop (SITL) support and common sensors simulation.

Our work demonstrates how to integrate these well-known tools with several utilities, enabling efficient data collection, drone control, autopilot simulation, realistic dynamic object movement, configurable static object placement, and more.

III. SIMULATION ARCHITECTURE

The complete simulation architecture is summarized in Fig. 2, where its main modules are depicted. The core of this architecture is strongly based on the ‘AirSim plugin’ working in Unreal Engine worlds, which manages the simulation within our context of UAVs.

AirSim is an open-source, cross-platform plugin that simulates UAV operation, controlling its actuators via communication with the ‘Autopilot SITL’, and emulating custom embedded sensors. Unreal Engine, on the other hand, is a 3D computer graphics game engine responsible for graphical rendering, collision calculations, and vehicle movement simulation. Additionally, AirSim provides an interface for real-time control of world objects. The ‘Assets Manager’ module utilizes this function to place and move objects in the world, allowing the real-time simulation of tailored dynamic and static obstacles without the need to define their behaviours in the Unreal Engine environment.

Another crucial aspect of the proposed architecture is the Robot Operating System (ROS), the primary framework for data collection and algorithm development. The ROS ecosystem is primarily utilized for its robust capabilities in node communication and its suite of robotics tools. For example, RViz provides a powerful graphical interface for visualizing data generated by UAV sensors. Additionally, ‘rosbags’ are essential utilities that record and replay all simulated data, facilitating offline algorithm training within this context. To integrate the simulation with ROS, two modules are employed. The ‘MavROS’ module establishes a ROS interface with the UAV autopilot, while the ‘AirSim ROS Wrapper’ module publishes data from the UAV and its embedded sensors.

A. Unreal Engine & AirSim

One of the primary aspects of simulation is the environment’s characteristics. Unreal Engine enables the creation of photorealistic worlds, replicating lights, textures, and reflections with high fidelity. This high level of realism is crucial for training and validating computer vision algorithms.

Unreal Engine 4.27 is utilized in conjunction with a customized version of the AirSim plugin. In this setup, compiled worlds are generated by packaging the projects for Linux, creating executables that can be launched independently without any additional dependencies. All Unreal Engine projects containing AirSim can be used interchangeably within our architecture, allowing us to switch between them by simply selecting the compiled project to be executed.

Our enhanced version of AirSim¹ exports the elapsed simulation time through its API, enabling synchronization with developed algorithms and ROS tools when the clock rate is not set to 1:1. This feature is particularly useful when simulated time passes faster or slower than real-time in order to accommodate different computing capabilities.

All sensors are listed in a configuration file, which our architecture processes to properly instantiate the sensors via the AirSim plugin.

¹<https://github.com/catec/AirSim>

B. LiDAR Noise Model

To enhance the performance of algorithms when transitioning from simulation to real robotic systems, we have identified a potential improvement for the sensors supported in AirSim. Currently, only the barometer and magnetometer incorporate a noise model. LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology is increasingly used in aerial robotics research due to the reduction in cost, size, and weight of available commercial models. Our custom version of AirSim includes an improved LiDAR sensor, which introduces a noise model designed to mimic the behaviour of real sensors. We will delve deeper into this noise model in the next section III-B.

The implemented noise model closely emulates the internal workings of a 3D LiDAR sensor. Most commercial LiDARs consist of several vertically arranged laser beams rotating at high speed. In most cases, the LiDAR driver fixes the horizontal and vertical angular resolutions to the theoretical values, producing 3D point clouds with no laser beam direction errors. However, range measurements depend on the beams' time of flight (ToF), which is more susceptible to errors due to environmental conditions and the internal clock resolution. These errors become more pronounced at greater distances, resulting in poorer performance as the beams hit more distant objects. Consequently, instead of adding random noise to each point, our model affects only the range, not the direction, of the beam. The range noise is modelled as a zero-mean Gaussian distribution with a standard deviation that increases linearly with the range.

Fig. 3: Comparison of point clouds between ideal and noisy LiDARs.

Since AirSim is open-source, the code for simulating a LiDAR within the Unreal Engine is available, allowing us to add this noise model to each point in the ray-tracing process. The source code is available in our previously introduced custom version of the AirSim plugin, as described in Section III-A. The parameters that can be modified externally are the standard deviation at zero distance and at the maximum range. Thus, a linear noise model has been implemented, generating the desired noisy point clouds by parameterizing the LiDAR sensors in the configuration file with these standard deviation values. In Fig. 3, the default LiDAR is simulated alongside a new one incorporating the proposed noise model, illustrating how this model affects the 3D position of the points.

C. AirSim ROS Wrapper

This module primarily publishes all simulated sensor data to the ROS ecosystem through communication with the AirSim API. Additionally, it is responsible for publishing the UAV's ground-truth pose and the positions of its sensors, as well as synchronizing all the data with the simulation time.

Fig. 4: Example of reference frames: graph view and 3D representation.

In order to ensure a consistent robotics coordinate framework, all reference frames are published in a Front-Left-Up (FLU) local system (X: Front, Y: Left, Z: Up) within the ROS TF tool. This tool handles transformations between various reference frames, facilitating algorithms to seamlessly process 3D poses across different coordinate systems. Moreover, for camera sensors, an additional reference frame is published, allowing the transformation of the camera body's FLU frame into an optical frame aligned with the lens (X: Left, Y: Down, Z: Forward), which is essential for computer vision tasks. Fig. 4, a depiction of a complete graph of reference frames is presented alongside a 3D view showcasing selected examples.

D. Flight Controller

AirSim supports SITL simulation with popular flight controllers (autopilots) such as PX4 or ArduPilot. A SITL module has been set up for the abovementioned flight controllers, allowing us to conveniently switch between them in our final architecture.

Autopilots typically accept a wide array of parameters that define their behaviour. In addition to configuring general parameters such as its acceleration capabilities, there is also an option to select the pose source, which is particularly noteworthy in our architecture. The pose source is essential for performing autonomous missions, as it allows the UAV to localize itself in the environment and navigate effectively. In this context, two sets of parameters are prepared for both autopilots to accommodate two different pose sources:

- GNSS-based localization: the flight controller utilizes the simulated GNSS signal provided by AirSim to compute the UAV's position, relying on the UAV's simulated Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) to determine its orientation relative to the magnetic north.
- External localization: the flight controller is prepared to accept externally computed pose. This capability is utilized to evaluate odometry algorithms (e.g. LiDAR inertial odometry) or to navigate using the AirSim's UAV ground-truth pose provided by the node detailed in Section III-C.

Fig. 5: Static and dynamic objects: visual landmarks configured to display CATEC’s logo (left) and a person following a parabolic ground trajectory (right).

As mentioned earlier, the ‘MavROS’ module facilitates bidirectional communication with the autopilot via the ROS framework, serving as a bridge. This node undergoes different behaviour based on the specific autopilot in use. To address this variability, another module is integrated above it. The UAV Abstraction Layer (UAL) [14] provides a high-level interface, abstracting away the differences between specific messages or data types. UAL also provides several utilities integrated into this simulation scheme. For example, it simulates a safety pilot, enabling the real UAV to arm and switch to autonomous mode. Other valuable utilities include recording and tracking waypoints, executing autonomous missions, and more.

E. Static & Dynamic Objects

In addition to the main UAV, our simulated environment includes various other objects that can be controlled through the AirSim plugin. Any object in the compiled project can be instantiated and positioned precisely within the environment. In this manner, we can customize the environment at runtime using AirSim’s API, eliminating the need to rebuild the Unreal Engine project to modify the behaviour of objects. We manage the reference frames so that every position is referenced to the UAV’s spawn point.

In this context, two different object management options are proposed. Objects that are placed in a fixed position with configurable size and texture are referred to as ‘static objects’. In contrast, objects that are controlled kinematically to move between a set of waypoints are referred to as ‘dynamic objects’. Several applications arise: while the former can be used to change the environment layout or generate visual landmarks, the latter can be treated as dynamic obstacles to develop, for example, detect-and-avoid algorithms.

As an example of these configurable ‘static objects’, Fig. 5 (left) shows a UAV flying over several visual landmarks featuring CATEC’s logo as their main texture. This concept can be extended to create visual landmarks using any other useful texture (e.g. QR codes), thus enabling numerous applications in robotics [15]. Similarly, since any other object can change its position and appearance, tasks such as switching between multiple layouts in a simulated warehouse are simplified.

The control of ‘dynamic objects’ involves positioning them along a precomputed trajectory, which is determined using a

series of configurable waypoints. As an example, in Fig. 5 (right), a person displaying a walking animation is controlled via a previously calculated trajectory.

All the calculated trajectories are primarily derived from the kinematics of Uniformly Accelerated Rectilinear Motion (UARM), Uniform Rectilinear Motion (URM), and Curvilinear Motion (CM). The combination of these motion types produces parabolic trajectories in the spatio-temporal domain. The generated motions feature a constant magnitude acceleration when applied, resulting in a trapezoidal velocity profile. An example of these spatio-temporal trajectories is shown in Fig. 6 (left), where straight lines and parabolas describe the positions of a plane travelling at constant speed through different waypoints.

Therefore, the inputs for this generic trajectory calculation process include a set of spatial waypoints (X, Y, Z positions), the desired cruising speed, and the available acceleration. The acceleration is used to modify either the magnitude or the direction of the velocity, enabling acceleration/deceleration of the object or smoothing transitions between waypoints.

The orientations can be addressed similarly, defining orientations in the set of waypoints, a maximum angular velocity, and an available angular acceleration. However, for most dynamic objects in this context, the orientations are directly related to the previously calculated positions. Refer to the scheme in 6 (right) to understand the following references regarding objects’ orientation. We distinguish two types:

- **Multicopter UAVs:** these vehicles allow an extra degree of freedom in yaw, while roll and pitch are generally influenced by their velocity in the XY world plane. The behaviour is simplified by adjusting roll and pitch proportionally to the projection of the velocity vector onto their perpendicular axes.
- **Moving-forward objects:** objects such as aircraft, cars, and even persons or animals, typically align their orientation with the direction of their motion. Therefore, pitch and yaw are computed to align the velocity direction with their forward axis (X), while roll remains at zero. For the specific case of aeroplanes, roll is computed by differentiating the yaw value, mimicking real-world aeroplane tilting. An example illustrating this orientation computation is shown in the graphs of Fig. 6 (middle).

Fig. 6: Aircraft trajectory example: position vs. time (left), orientation vs. time (middle), axis references, and 3D trajectory view (right).

Combining all these concepts, several types of trajectories can be generated. An example is shown in Fig. 6, illustrating a complete trajectory generated for an aeroplane, including its positions, orientations, and a 3D view. Feasible trajectories can be built for a wide range of objects, allowing for the simulation of rich dynamic environments for multiple purposes.

IV. DEPLOYMENT AND RESULTS

To deploy the architecture, the entire system uses Docker [16], a platform that packages applications and their dependencies into standardized units called containers. This enhances efficiency, deployment, and scaling. Thus, the core functionalities are pre-packaged into independent Docker images:

- ‘Simulator’ Docker image is based on an Ubuntu image with properly configured graphics drivers. It includes the compiled Unreal Engine projects and is designed to run the selected simulation executable, forming the core of the simulation scheme.
- ‘AirSim’ Docker image includes ROS and the AirSim API, containing processes such as the ‘AirSim ROS Wrapper’ and ‘Assets Manager’ shown in Fig. 2. The purpose of this container is to export sensor data and manage simulation objects using the AirSim API and the ROS tools.
- ‘SITL’ Docker image contains the Software-In-The-Loop (SITL) application for the selected flight controller. It supports both ArduPilot and PX4 SITL, allowing for easy switching between both.
- ‘Onboard’ Docker image includes the base code in the ROS framework that runs on the onboard computer of the UAV. Our standard configuration for this image includes ‘MavROS’ and ‘UAL’ for autopilot communication and abstraction, respectively. Additionally, it can be enhanced with specific algorithms, depending on the project requirements.

Each Docker image described is instantiated to create its corresponding Docker container. Inside each container, different processes are executed to enable the detailed functionality.

The main connections between these Docker containers are summarized in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Docker architecture for simulation deployment.

To validate the functionalities, a refinery scenario depicted in Fig. 8a was prepared, providing a compiled project with configurable visual landmarks and animated walking figures. Both objects can be instantiated at runtime, serving as examples of static and dynamic object types. Additionally, any available AirSim sensor can be integrated into the UAV system through the corresponding configuration file. For this testing environment, a LiDAR sensor and a camera were chosen as embedded sensors. Fig. 8b and 8c display the ROS-integrated outputs of these sensors. Using only simulated LiDAR data, the UAV’s pose can be computed using lightweight state-of-the-art SLAM algorithms such as LeGO-LOAM [17]. With the estimated pose, fully autonomous missions can be executed, allowing the UAV to navigate through several waypoints. The trajectory and the resulting map are depicted in Fig. 8d.

The simulation time rate is fully controllable until it is limited by the computational capabilities. An Ouster OS1 LiDAR with 32 vertical laser beams and a horizontal resolution of 512 measurements was implemented. The time rate was set to 0.6x, achieving adequate performance on a Dell XPS 15 7590 equipped with an Intel i7 9th Gen processor, 16 GB of RAM, and an Nvidia GeForce GTX 1650 GPU.

Fig. 8: Algorithms validation in a refinery environment for a simulated autonomous mission.

The complete deployment of the simulator architecture is presented in this demo video². The video demonstrates the configuration of sensors and objects while selecting the specified environment. Various visual landmarks and animated walking figures are also configured by specifying their positions in the corresponding files. Since no localization algorithms are running in this demo, the flight controller uses the AirSim ground-truth UAV pose to navigate through the environment. UAV teleoperation via keyboard is also available through a utility in the UAL ecosystem. In this demo video, this utility is used to manually navigate the UAV.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The outcome of this research is a comprehensive simulation architecture, enabling realistic UAV simulations across a broad spectrum of scenarios and configurations. This work emphasizes the following key points:

- Realistic simulation of flight controller behaviour using SITL of the popular autopilots ArduPilot and PX4.
- Simulation of enhanced sensors through AirSim Unreal Plugin, including a new realistic noise model for the default LiDAR sensor.
- Integration with the ROS ecosystem to facilitate the validation of control and perception algorithms, allowing easy deployment of autonomous missions.
- General management of object motion in the environment, enabling placement of static objects in specified locations and control of dynamic objects using precomputed feasible trajectories.
- Abstraction of the operating system via Docker images, encapsulating applications within isolated containers.
- High configurability of the system through high-level configuration files, enabling flexible customization of parameters and settings.
- Photorealistic simulations through Unreal Engine capabilities.

By leveraging these capabilities, researchers and developers can efficiently prototype, test, and refine aerial robotics systems in a controlled and versatile virtual environment.

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²<https://youtu.be/BtLabqV6eug>

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